

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEFENSE STYLE MECHANISM OF THE STUDENTS (AZEIRBAIJAN CASE)

Aliyeva G.

*Baku State University,
Social science and psychology faculty, PhD student*

Abstract

The present study explores defense styles of the students. The psychometric properties of the Defense Style Questionnaire (DSQ-40), used for assessing students' defense styles, are also explored. Participants in this study were undergraduates studying in a social science and psychology faculty.

The literature review described the main approaches and previous researches results about this problem.

Result. Majority of the students' defense style are maladaptive such immature, and neurotic. Undoing, projection, passive aggression, acting out and somatization dominated among the defense styles. The students who demonstrated mature defense style as humor, suppression, sublimation, their academic achievement were higher than others. This fact let us concentrate students behavior and improve their reflective thinking abilities for future successes.

Keywords: defense styles, university students, mature defense style, immature defense style

Introduction

The defense style problem has received attention over the past century, authors (Cramer, 1991; Fenichel, 1945; A. Freud, 1936; S. Freud, 1894; Kernberg, 1976; Klein, 1973; Vaillant, 1971, 1975, 1976) searched that issue with different population. Freud described ego defense mechanisms are mental mechanisms that have function so as to protect the person from internal and external stressors. He mentioned altruism, displacement, dissociation, distortion, humor, intellectualization, passive-aggression, projection, psychotic denial, reaction formation, repression, schizoid fantasy, suppression, and sublimation.

In the second part of the 20th century, Klein (1973), Kernberg (1976) and Vaillant analyzed eight defense styles: acting out, anticipation, fantasy, primitive idealization, identification, denial, splitting, and devaluation. Vaillant explained defense mechanisms as "involuntary coping mechanisms" (Vaillant, 2011). Another word, defense mechanisms were investigated as being non-conscious, unintentional and trait like processes. The authors explained the defense styles from maladaptive to adaptive: immature, image-distorting, neurotic, mature.

The immature style - projection, passive aggression, autistic-fantasy, somatization, displacement and acting out. It describes maladaptive action patterns.

The image distorting style - denial, dissociation, splitting, isolation and devaluation. In some articles devaluation was described as immature defense style.

Neurotic style - undoing, pseudoaltruism, idealization and reaction formation. Vaillant mentioned it as threatening ideas, feelings, memories, wishes, or fears out of awareness (Vaillant, 2011).

Mature Style - sublimation, humor, anticipation and suppression. This style associated with high level of coping, and associated with a constructive type of mastery of the conflict.

K.Evangelia and colleagues investigated defense style and learning opportunities among university stu-

dents, and compared Grade Point Average (GPA). Authors mentioned mature, immature, neurotic and image distorting defense style, also deep, strategic and surface learning approach (Evangelia et.al, 2018). The research results indicate a mature/adaptive and an immature/maladaptive learning pattern. Authors highlighted that deep and strategic approach, also high level of GPA associated mature defense style, more adaptive behavior pattern. But surface learning way of students related to neurotic, immature and also image distorting defense style (Evangelia et.al, 2018). There was a negative correlation between GPA and maladaptive learning pattern, also neurotic defense style ($r=-0,006$, $r=-0,052$). The positive strong correlation was found out between mature behavior patterns (sublimation, humor, anticipation, suppression) and GPA results ($r=0.160^{**}$, $p<0.001$) (Evangelia et.al, 2018).

Previous studies indicate relation learning approach and emotional stability (Chamorro-Premuzic et al.,2007), coping ways (Sandover and colleagues, 2015), and different emotions as positive and negative aspect (Trigwell et al., 2012). Students who prefer deep learning their emotional state, daily mood and coping ways were higher than the others.

Kumar S. searched this problem among Indian students in 11 colleges (Kumar S., 2016). He examined previous literature material related to defense mechanism and learning process. According to literature materials author mentioned relation between defense style and learning abilities of the students. The descriptive and differentiated analysis defined correlation between career choosing value and defense styles. Students whose defense patterns were adaptive than other, their career choosing test figures (CCI-5 questionnaire) were higher than others; and there wasn't significant difference related to their gender:

Boys: Mature factor (70,18±12,97), Neurotic factor (71,94±7,14), Immature factor (68,32±7,31)

Girls: Mature factor (70,26±9,33), Neurotic factor (72,38±6,09), Immature factor (67,84±8,07) (Kumar S., 2016).

Research questions: The main target of the paper was to identify defense style of the students, and behavior pattern. Thus the study raises the following questions:

- What kinds of defense style dominate students' behavior?
- Is there any difference students' fixation in various situation?
- Are there any relation between defense style and fixation obstacle, fixation self-defense and fixation satisfaction needs?

Methods:

Instruments/ Materials: Measuring defense was realized by projective techniques, clinical rating system, self-report questionnaire. The DSQ-40 is the most widely used questionnaire although its psychometric properties remain to be improved (Giovazolias et al., 2017).

The Defense Style Questionnaire (DSQ) is a frequently used self-report instrument for defense measurement (Bond, 2004) and has been translated and validated in numerous languages (e.g., Chinese, Dutch, Egyptian Arabic, Finnish, French, German, Italian, Norwegian) (Bond, 2000). Originally developed by Bond and his colleagues (1983), it was designed to operationalize and assess conscious manifestations of defenses.

The DSQ-40 assesses 20 different defenses (see Table 1) that are categorized into one of three factors: mature (4 defenses; 8 items), immature (12 defenses; 24 items), or neurotic (4 defenses; 8 items). Respondents rate individual agreement on 40 statements that

correspond to the defense styles, agreement is rated on a 9 point Likert scale, with labels of agreement confined to each end of the scale, 1 = "strongly disagree" and 9 = "strongly agree".

The next assessment tool is Rosenzweig Frustration Test (RFT). It is a projective test that was created with the purpose to verify, under a frustrating situation, and this projective instrument consists of 24 situations. The responses are classified according to the direction of aggression (extraaggression, intraaggression, imagergression) and type of reaction (fixation obstacle, fixation self-defense, fixation satisfaction of need).

The statistics were performed using the SPSS software program.

Procedure: After the approval of the research by the Department of Gender and Applied Psychology at Baku State University, survey materials were shared via software program. The cover letter was sent with explanation of the research objectives, and also highlighting that the information would be kept confidential.

There are some **limitations** of the study:

- the limited number of the students;
- the survey was shared with only students at BSU;
- so the results can be assigned only for this participants.

Results and conclusion:

The survey material and link (Rosenzweig Frustration Test) were shared among 45 students (2nd year of the faculty) and 38 students of them completed the tests. The descriptive statistics were demonstrated in the following table:

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of the variables.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
extraaggression	3	50	17,07	11,674
intraaggression	21	62	39,30	12,191
imagergression	17	75	52,73	13,475
Fixation obstacle	8	46	31,42	12,339
Fixation self defense	4	50	25,21	13,117
Fixation satisfaction of need	25	88	49,16	13,977
mature defense style	28,00	100,00	73,1447	18,57414
immature defense style	25,00	68,70	44,0368	12,69558
neurotic defense style	12,50	87,50	53,7368	15,41092
image distorting defense style	12,50	75,00	47,5132	16,43147

Extra aggression level of the students' was the least one, when their aggression controlling skills dominated; $17,07 \pm 11,6$ and $52,73 \pm 13,47$ respectively. Intra aggression figures of them fluctuated min.21 max 62; $39,3 \pm 12,19$. This fact let us think about the reasons of their intra aggression of the young population, although their adjusting behavior was more than others.

During the stressed situation majority of them concentrate to satisfy own needs, while their fixation of self defense was the least one, $25,21 \pm 13,11$.

The students defense style analyzed using DSQ-40 questionnaire results, and the mature defense (humor, sublimation, anticipation and suppression) was most noticed, while the neurotic symptoms were the second one; $73,14 \pm 18,57$ and $53,73 \pm 15,41$ respectively. Maximum figures of the neurotic defense style was 87,5, so this fact demand future special investigating and correction program.

There was negative correlation between mature defense style and extra aggression, and positive correlation between aggression solving behavior model and mature defense style ($r = -0,237$; $r = 0,82$). These students

concentrate on obstacle, or the situation, $r=0,241$. But the results could be applied in this group participations, because the p value wasn't justified.

Correlation between intraaggression and immature defense style was significantly strong negative, $r=-$

$0,597$; $p<0,005$. The increasing extra aggression correlated fixation self defense positively, too ($r=0,614^{**}$, $p<0,001$). Correlation among different variables examined in the following tables.

Table 2

Correlation among variables.

Defense style and aggression

	Extraaggression	Intraaggression	Imaggression
Mature defense style	-0.237	-0.056	0.82
Immature defense style	-0.010	-0.597*	-0.006
Neurotic defense style	-0.292	-0.354	0.110
Image distorting defense style	0.261	-0.083	-0.287

$p<0,005$; $p<0,001$

Defense style and fixation

	Fixation obstacle	Fixation self defense	Fixation sat. need
Mature defense style	0.241	-0.422	0.05
Immature defense style	-0.047	-0.087	-0.350
Neurotic defense style	-0.331	-0.077	0.039
Image distorting defense style	-0.068	-0.310	0.152

$p<0,005$; $p<0,001$

Aggression and fixation

	Fixation obstacle	Fixation self defense	Fixation sat. need
Extraaggression	-0.316	0.614**	-0.294
Intraaggression	0.448	0.092	-0.068
Imaggression	0.423	-0.345	0.286

$p<0,005$; $p<0,001$

The defense style mechanism results were examined using confirmatory factor analysis, the mature, and immature defense style were eigenvalues that the figures were more one, 1,216 and 1,031,

respectively. Their percentage of variance and cumulative percentage, also rotation sums were summarized following table and correlation factors described in the figure 1.

Figure 1. factor analysis on DSQ-40

Neurotic defense style, also in aggression of the students lead further mental, interpersonal relationship problems such as anxiety, depression, low self esteem, lack of empathy, role conflict, and deviant behavior patterns.

Recommendation: the following items were summarized based on literature review and survey results:

- defense mechanisms play an important role in students' adaptation and achievement at the university; so the students need to get comprehensive information about their defense style, EQ, and source of aggression;
- the students need to be involved emotional-support programs, that help to improve their emotional regulation skills;
- further detailed study should be explored neurotic and image-distorting defense style of the students;
- The generalizability of the results of this study are limited by its cross-sectional nature, participants at BSU only; so the research should be expanded with more participations, and get more detailed statistical calculations according DSQ-40 material;

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

Financial Disclosure: The authors declared that this study received no financial support.

Acknowledgements

My deepest gratitude is extended to the students who took part in survey. I am extremely appreciative of their participation.

References

1. Carvalho AF, Hyphantis TN, Taunay TC, Macêdo DS, Floros GD, Ottoni GL, Fountoulakis KN, Lara DR (2013). The relationship between affective temperaments, defensive styles and depressive symptoms in a large sample. *J Affect Disord.*;146:58–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2012.08.038>.
2. Cramer, P., and Tracy, A. (2005). The pathway from child personality to adult adjustment: the road is not straight. *J. Res. Pers.* 39, 369–394.
3. Karagiannopoulou, E., Milienos, F.S., & Athanasopoulos, V.D. (2018). Associations Between Defense Styles, Approaches to Learning, and Achievement Among University Students. *Frontiers in Education*.
4. Karagiannopoulou, E. Vlachopanou, P, Tsiampalis, T. Association among defense mechanisms, causes of procrastination and well-being; Gender differences, *European Journal of Public Health*, Volume 29, Issue Supplement_4, November 2019, ckz186.584, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckz186.584>
5. Kember, D., Leung, D., and McNaught, C. (2008). A workshop activity to demonstrate that approaches to learning are influenced by the teaching and learning environment. *Active Learn. High. Educ.* 9, 43–56.
6. Giovazolias, T., Karagiannopoulou, E., & Mitsopoulou, E. (2017). Can the Factor Structure of Defense Style Questionnaire (DSQ-40) Contribute to Our Understanding of Parental Acceptance/Rejection, Bullying, Victimization and Perceived Well-Being in Greek Early Adolescents?. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 13(2), 269-285. <https://doi.org/10.5964/ejop.v13i2.1090>
7. Rios-Garcia LR, Cook PE. Self-derogation and defense style in college students. *J Pers Assess.* 1975 Jun;39(3):273-81. doi: 10.1207/s15327752jpa3903_9. PMID: 1185496.
8. Vaillant GE, Bond M, Vaillant CO. An Empirically Validated Hierarchy of Defense Mechanisms. *Arch Gen Psychiatry.* 1986;43(8):786–794. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.1986.01800080072010
9. Wagas, A., Naveed, S., Aedma, K.K., Tariq, M. and Afzaal, T.(2018). Exploring clusters of defense styles, psychiatric symptoms and academic achievements among medical students: a cross-sectional study in Pakistan. *BMC Research Notes* 11(782).